

TRANSFORMATION OF THE LIBRARY: FROM TRADITIONAL TECHNICAL MEANS TO A PROACTIVE DIGITAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. *This article examines the transformation of modern academic libraries from traditional technical systems into proactive digital environments. It analyzes the main technological tools used in contemporary library practice, including RFID identification, self-service terminals, automated return stations, robotic storage and retrieval systems, digitization equipment, OCR technologies, mobile applications, smart lockers, visitor counters, and social robots. Particular attention is given to how these tools improve collection management, inventory accuracy, preservation of physical documents, user access, and service efficiency. The article also reviews major international professional events, including IFLA WLIC, the ALA Annual Conference, and Computers in Libraries, where innovative library solutions are regularly presented. The study shows that digital technologies reduce manual labor, expand 24/7 access to resources, support personalized services, and change the overall model of library work, making libraries more automated, flexible, accessible, and user-oriented in the context of global digital transformation and responding to contemporary academic information needs effectively.*

Keywords: *digitization of collections, automated libraries, RFID technology, IFLA, ALA.*

INTRODUCTION

At present, academic libraries of higher educational institutions are actively developing and improving their material and technical base by introducing modern technologies. The technical means of library activity do not constitute a completed list: they continue to develop together with digital technologies, changing not only individual processes but also the very model of library work. If, at the end of the twentieth century, automation was mainly reduced to transferring card catalogs into electronic format and introducing the first databases, today it concerns qualitatively different solutions. They affect all key areas:

Fig. 1. Library technologies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The methodological basis of the study includes descriptive, comparative, and analytical methods. The research is based on the analysis of modern technical tools used in academic libraries, including RFID systems, self-service terminals, automated storage and retrieval systems, digitization technologies, mobile applications, and robotic solutions. Materials from international library exhibitions and conferences, including IFLA WLIC, the ALA Annual Conference, and Computers in Libraries, were also examined.

RESULTS

One of the most widespread modern tools has become RFID (Radio Frequency Identification) technology. Each item of the collection is equipped with an electronic tag, whose data are read automatically during lending, return, or inventory and synchronized with the automated library information system (ALIS). Mobile RFID readers make it possible to carry out inventory directly at the shelf, without removing books from the shelves; this reduces staff labor costs by ten to twenty times compared with barcoding [1]. Anti-theft gates at the exit simultaneously perform a security function and keep a count of attendance [2]. According to studies, after implementing RFID, libraries record a reduction in labor costs of about 30%, while the accuracy of inventory accounting approaches 99% [3].

Self-service terminals have also become widespread. They allow the reader to process lending and return independently: the operation is recorded through a built-in RFID reader, and the terminal prints a receipt [4].

A separate variety consists of outdoor automatic return stations operating around the clock and parcel lockers outside the library: in university buildings, shopping centers, and residential districts. The reader places an order through the electronic catalog and collects the book using a QR code at a convenient time [5]. In a number of libraries, the share of operations performed through terminals reaches 94% of the total number of transactions.

Figure 2. The BookBot robotic system at the University of New South Wales Library (Australia)

In libraries that use automated storage and retrieval systems, the collection is organized differently. Documents are placed in a high-density closed storage facility consisting of multi-tiered blocks up to 10-15 meters high; upon request from the electronic catalog, a special crane retrieves the required container and delivers it to the circulation desk [6].

The BookBot system at the University of New South Wales Library can hold from 100,000 to 1 million items while occupying an area several times smaller than ordinary shelving [33]. Here, books are arranged not by subject but by size in order to use space as densely as possible. In open halls, navigation and consultation functions are assumed by mobile robots: Pepper, produced by SoftBank Robotics, conducts dialogue in 15 languages, searches the catalog, and sends the results to the reader's phone [7].

Digitization of collections solves a task that previously seemed almost insoluble: ensuring both the preservation of the original and broad access to its content [35]. Planetary scanners with a V-shaped cradle capture images without pressure on the binding; the productivity of automatic systems reaches 3,000 pages per hour [36]. OCR programs recognize text and make the document available for full-text search. As a result, the physical original no longer wears out from repeated use, while its digital copy is available to an unlimited number of users simultaneously [8].

DISCUSSION

Taken together, modern technical means cover the entire cycle of working with a document, from its arrival in the collection to its delivery to the reader in physical or digital form. The latest developments are regularly presented at major professional exhibitions and conferences, which provide an understanding of the direction in which the technological development of librarianship is moving.

A key place in the global library community is occupied by two organizations: IFLA and ALA. The International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA) was founded in 1927 and unites library organizations from more than 140 countries. In the sphere of technology, IFLA develops metadata standards and formats for document description, publishes guidelines on digital libraries and the long-term preservation of electronic resources, and promotes the introduction of open access. Each year, the federation holds the World Library and Information Congress (IFLA WLIC), the largest global event in the library sphere, combining a scholarly program with a professional exhibition. In 2025, the congress was held in Central Asia for the first time, in Astana, Kazakhstan, gathering more than 1,600 delegates from over 110 countries [9].

Figure 3. Exhibits at the IFLA WLIC 2025 professional exhibition, Astana: selfCheck 3000 kiosk (Bibliotheca), transport system (Telelift), and tablet solution (Hublet)

At the exhibition, Bibliotheca presented several new products:

- the selfCheck 3000 self-service kiosk: a terminal through which the reader independently borrows and returns books without contacting a librarian; it is intended for libraries with a large number of visitors;
- the compact selfCheck 2500 model: a similar smaller kiosk for small libraries or spaces with limited floor area;
- the cloudCheck Tablet solution: the same self-service function, but implemented on a tablet that can be placed in any convenient location without fixed installation;
- the flexAMH system: a device that independently accepts returned books, recognizes them, and sorts them by category, freeing employees from this routine work.

Telelift demonstrated transport systems for moving documents inside the library, an analogue of a conveyor delivering books between departments without staff participation; Hublet presented a solution for lending tablets to readers for temporary use directly in the library hall [10].

The American Library Association (ALA) was founded in 1876 and is the oldest and largest library organization in the world, uniting more than 50,000 members. ALA develops professional standards and ethical norms for the use of digital tools, publishes thematic guidelines and studies, and participates in shaping policy in the field of copyright and open access. The annual ALA Annual Conference is the largest professional library event in the world; within its framework, the Library Marketplace exhibition is held, bringing together hundreds of suppliers of library solutions.

In 2025, the conference was held in Philadelphia and included more than 800 vendors [38]. Among the developments presented, the Romi robot from Bibliotheca stands out. Romi is a child-sized device that:

- moves around the hall independently;
- helps readers find the book they need;
- accepts returns;
- accompanies visitors to the required shelf.

Romi charges from an ordinary power outlet and is currently undergoing beta testing after successful implementation in libraries in Japan and South Korea.

Figure 4. Exhibits at the Library Marketplace, ALA Annual Conference 2025, Philadelphia: Romi robotic assistant (Bibliotheca) and AutoLend kiosk (International Library Services)

International Library Services presented AutoLend kiosks, devices for the automatic lending of books that operate without staff participation. During the natural disasters in Los Angeles in 2025, these kiosks continued to serve readers in the affected areas when the ordinary operation of libraries had been disrupted [11]. One of the main topics of the conference was the use of artificial intelligence in library activity, including discussions of algorithmic bias and the environmental consequences of using AI systems [12].

Among professional events, the Computers in Libraries conference stands out; it has been held for about 40 years and is devoted to the practical aspects of introducing digital technologies

in libraries. In 2025, the event was held in Arlington, Virginia, USA, and included more than 100 thematic sessions and over 40 solution providers [13].

Figure 5. Exhibitors and technology companies presented at Computers in Libraries 2025

D-Tech International presented several developments:

SMART lockers are modular cabinets with a touch screen and an intelligent access system, allowing the reader independently to receive an ordered book, borrow a laptop or tablet for temporary use, or pick up pre-reserved materials. The lockers are installed both indoors and outdoors for 24/7 operation and are integrated with the library management system [41].

The appIT mobile application allows the reader to borrow and renew a book directly from a smartphone through RFID or barcode scanning, without approaching a terminal; the application also displays information about debts, available reservations, and library opening hours [14].

The countIT visitor counter consists of ceiling sensors based on time-of-flight technology, which record the actual flow of people through the entrance with an accuracy of 99.8%, without collecting personal data and without using cameras. This enables the library to monitor occupancy, plan staff work, and justify funding [15].

Meescan presented a self-service system combining a kiosk and a mobile application: the reader can process lending either through a device in the library or through a phone, and the system itself is installed without complex technical preparation. This makes it possible to introduce it even in small libraries with limited resources [16].

The development of technical means for libraries does not stop: every new generation of devices expands the possibilities of automation, reduces dependence on manual labor, and makes library services more accessible to different categories of users.

CONCLUSION

Thus, the transformation of libraries from traditional technical systems to proactive digital environments is connected with the active introduction of RFID technologies, automated storage systems, digitization tools, self-service platforms, mobile applications, and robotic assistants. These technologies improve service quality, reduce staff workload, expand access to resources, and make library services more flexible and user-oriented. Therefore, the further development of library technologies will continue to play an important role in the modernization of academic libraries.

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